

CHALLENGES OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN BANGALORE: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Skill development policy of Karnataka is guided by the principles of 'Equity' where the most marginalized and disadvantaged groups based on caste, religion, disability, gender, culture or ethnic affiliation and/or any such phenomena shall get a priority and strategies would be made to reach them proactively respecting their rights. The principles of 'Equality' shall be ensured where everyone will have fair and equal chance to get the benefits and advantage of this policy. 'Enlighten, Equip and Empower' this 3Es would guide the concept of skill development. The stakeholders shall be enlightened about the need for skilling, entrepreneurship development, and sustainable livelihood. The choice of opportunity will be provided in the spirit of human development and primary stakeholders would be empowered to get gainful and sustainable livelihood opportunity. Skill development would always maintain 'Futuristic' attitude and constantly update strategy, approach and activities to match the future need and changing dynamics. 'Complementing resources and strength through convergence' would be the key principle.

Key words: Skill Development, Sustainable Development, Entrepreneurship development, equality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Basically, skill development refers to the time spent on improving one's expertise and making future-ready, as well as any agilities pursued as a passion, and the capacity to execute a task with higher rate of success at the appropriate moment. It is crucial since one's abilities define their ability to carry out their intentions and goals successfully. In today's society, a lack of sufficient education and training limits people's prospects for self-improvement by preventing them from obtaining well-paying jobs. This eventually prohibits such persons from having a significant impact on economic growth. As a result, sufficient education quality and training are seen as critical components in dismantling the poverty eco-system. One individual, Sweta Mishra, has correctly said that "Skill development is no longer a matter of choice." Adapting, surviving, and succeeding are critical." India has a literacy rate of 74.04%, which is lower than that of some of the world's least developed countries, and just 46.2% of its citizens are employable. Literacy encompasses not only schooling but also the concept of skills, which includes technical knowledge, vocational skills, transferable skills, digital skills, and other knowledge and abilities necessary for job and living. According to a poll, just 25% of the Indian workforce has participated in a skill development programme, despite the fact that India requires a large number of qualified workers. In this era, many organizations preferred skilled individuals over less trained employees because skilled employees have excellent career advancement opportunities and helps in develop the organisation, in the same way that proficient personnel do. Skills boost productivity and quality of work, resulting in more substantial outcomes. According to the World Trade Organization (WTO), if India concentrates on skill development and training, its GDP might expand by 3% to 5% by 2035. India has a pressing need to train and cultivate skills in youths for advancement of the country.

The government of every state must recognize the youth's potential and offer them the support by providing them with the necessary advice, infrastructure, chances, and motivation to pursue their goals. Their zeal, abilities, strong critical awareness of the present world, and willingness to play a decisive role can all help to transform the world into a better place if they are guided in the proper path. Karnataka, a state known for its entrepreneurial drive, accounts for a large percentage of national industrial investment and production. The state has also become the country's technology and start-up capital. In the face of worldwide competition, the state recognizes the need of skill training and continual skill upgrade and encourages educational institutions to implement quantitative and qualitative metrics for capacity building.

II. LITTERATEUR REVIEW

1. **Okada (2012) [1]** reviews the current state of education, skills development, and employment for Indian youth, and considers the challenges facing India's skills development system. Drawing from the experience of Karnataka, one of India's most industrially developed states; the paper discusses recent initiatives to facilitate young people's transition to the world of work. It was found that while India has a well-institutionalized system of vocational training, it hasn't sufficiently prepared its youth with the skills that today's industries require. Thus, to speed its economic growth and take advantage of its "demographic dividend," the country has recently embarked on drastic policy reforms to accelerate skills development. These reforms have led to important changes, both in the national institutional framework and at the institutional level.
2. **Punjani (2014) [2]** investigated that whether introduction of Make in India project and other initiatives taken by the government is working as a key engine for India's economic growth or their contribution is not significant. It was found that Planning Commission report suggests only 10% of the Indian workforce get formal training and against the actual industrial training requirement of 22 million workers, only 4.3 million workers are getting trained! The existing skill development policy in India needs an urgent treatment. The institutional structure needs simplification with greater investment in training infrastructure and an emphasis on supporting a casual labour force that needs to be accompanied with incentives for private sector participation too. Put simply, for the success of "Make in India" project it is important to equip India's youthful millions with the right skills to compete in a global race for jobs.
3. **Das, Chandra, Kochhar and Kumar (2015)** Opined that female labor force participation in India is lower than many other emerging market economies, and has been declining since the mid-2000s. Moreover, there is a large gap in the labor force participation rates of men and women in India. This gender gap should be narrowed to fully harness India's demographic dividend. In addition, a related literature also finds that greater economic participation of women leads to higher economic growth.
4. **Deka and Batra (2016) [4]** reviewed the twelve research papers and found that manufacturing in India by foreign & domestic Industries in various sectors can generate employment opportunity. So, the Indian labour and prospective employees need to acquire skill and knowledge to gain employability. They also found that for the successful implementation of "Make in India" initiative, it is also important to implement various skill development initiatives to lower down the skill gap between the available skills and desired skills.
5. **Kanchan and Varshney (2015) [5]** studies and analyses the present status of skill development and the challenges India faces while implementation of different initiatives and strategies. They found during the course of study that presently 80% of the workforce in India (rural and urban)

doesn't possess any identifiable and marketable skills. Therefore, bridging this gap through various skill development initiatives could make India the global hub for skilled manpower, and also result in a surplus of skilled manpower of approximately 47 million 2020. Moreover, it is important that the intended beneficiaries of the skill development program join training programs with an inspiration to learn and make them self-reliant to live a better life.

6. **Kapur (2014)** tries to investigate the different information about the concept of skill development in India and the programs and policies that have been initiated for this purpose. It was found in the study that skill development has been facilitated by the organization of certain programs, educational institutions and training centers. Skills are of various kinds, within an organizational structure it is essential on the part of the management to develop leadership skills amongst themselves such as motivating people, decision making and communication. In India, rural masses are still in a backward condition, steps therefore have been implemented to develop skills amongst them for the purpose of obtaining self-sufficiency in resource utilization, governance and leadership. The different kinds of other skills which can open ways towards development of the individuals are literacy skills, computer skills, craftsmanship, manufacturing, trading skills and so forth.
7. **Kaur(2016)** ^[7] tried to study the future demand of skilled labour in the manufacturing sector of India and its corresponding supply. It also studies various obstacles in providing the requisite skills to the people of India and various initiatives taken by the government so far. It was explored that to train such a huge work-force can make India a prosperous nation. With "Make in India" the job creation process is going to accelerate. So "Skill India" is on its mission to impart the skills to the Indian youth to reap the rich demographic dividend. The government of India has taken various steps in this direction. But there are various challenges that demand more efforts from the government. Solving these problems can lead to the economic growth of the nation as the opportunity of demographic dividend is the best phase for a nation to boost its growth.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the present skill capacity of Bangalore, Karnataka
2. To study the challenges faced by skill development system in Karnataka.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is primarily descriptive in nature. It is solely based on secondary data and information gathered from relevant sources in accordance with the requirements. Skill India website, articles etc.

❖ PRESENT SCENARIO OF SKILL CAPACITY OF KARNATAKA

In order to reap the benefits of the demographic dividend, the state of Karnataka must provide its employees with the necessary skills. As a result, this section reflects the current skill levels of the Indian workforce in the 15-59 year age range in terms of their general educational and occupational training levels.

- The drop-out rates of educational institutions were estimated to be 63 percent in the age group of 5-14 years and 88 percent after 15 years of age, whereas the workforce participation rate rises rapidly after 14 years of age, resulting in a semi-literate workforce that struggles to absorb higher levels of skills.
- 25 percent of the Indian workforce is illiterate, 15 percent has a primary or secondary

education, and the remaining 23 percent has a secondary or higher education.

- 54.65% of Karnataka's workforce lacks employable skills
- In comparison to Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, and Uttarpradesh, just roughly 9% of new entrants to the labour force have obtained formal vocational training and 36% have received non-formal vocational training, implying that very few new entrants to the labour force have any marketable skills.
- In a nutshell, despite significant advances in terms of literacy, the high incidence of illiteracy continues to handicap Karnataka's workforce today. The foregoing statistics serve as a clear reminder that if skills are not offered to both new and existing workers, Karnataka's demographic dividend might quickly turn into a demographic nightmare. As a result, skill development programmes must expand their capacity and capabilities. Both the government and its partner agencies have taken various measures/initiatives in this area to ensure that the skill development system is implemented effectively throughout the state. However, Karnataka still has a number of outstanding difficulties and challenges that policymakers must address immediately.

❖ CHALLENGES OF KARNATAKA'S SKILL DEVELOPMENT

Despite several concerted efforts, the skill development mission remains a long distance from completion due to the presence of several severe key difficulties in the program's path. Some of these obstacles, as well as potential remedies, are listed below.

- **Insufficient knowledge base and information asymmetry:** In Karnataka, both the supply and demand sides have insufficient knowledge about the full skill eco-system. There is no precise mapping of the skills necessary by region/district, and no central disaggregated registration of the types of skilled workers needed in the business. Information asymmetry refers to a lack of knowledge about employable talents and employers among potential skill aspirants. Employers may be aware of specific skills needed for increased production, but they may not know where to find them.
- **Regional imbalances:** Karnataka faces challenges such as demographic variety, geographical distances, and underdeveloped support eco-systems and infrastructures, particularly in the state's northern regions. This challenge cannot be solved solely by a skill policy; it requires bodies and special purpose entities, such as the Hyderabad Karnataka Development Board, to address it in a comprehensive and coordinated manner.
- **Low Educational Attainment:** Despite the fact that the state has achieved progress in terms of educational attainment, as seen below: In Karnataka, there are around 76,744 schools with a total enrolment of 1, 03, 77,380 pupils (from pre-primary to high/senior secondary levels), indicating that schools have the highest number of enrolments. There are approximately 3803 colleges in the higher education sector. Students enrolled in open universities and other diploma programmer's account for 32% of the total student population. In Karnataka, vocational training is mostly provided by government and commercial industrial training institutes (ITIs). In the state, there are 1,777 public and private ITIs (258 government, 196 government-aided, and 1323 private), with a total capacity of 106,000 youth. However, at 68.9%, the percentage of actual enrolment to total capacity is low. In the state, there are approximately 290 polytechnics with a total enrolment capacity of 75,000 students; the actual enrolment to capacity ratio is approximately 80%.

- **Vocational Training:** While Karnataka is gradually moving towards a knowledge economy, where skills are widely recognized as an important lever of economic growth, the perception of vocational education remains skewed, implying that it is primarily for those who have been denied admission to the formal system. As a result, it will take some time before it is deemed a viable alternative to conventional schooling.
- **Women's skill development:** Women make up a significant and vital portion of the workforce in Karnataka; however their share of the total labour force is decreasing.
- **Participation of the private sector:** The current position in terms of private sector participation is as follows: The private sector is not sufficiently involved in the development of educational and vocational training curricula and policy design. Because the majority of private sector institutes are located in urban regions, the rural population continues to fall behind. Furthermore, the poorer or disadvantaged sections of society are unable to obtain sufficient skill training due to the high expense of these institutes.
- **Placement-linked Challenge:** A key flaw in Karnataka's current skill (or education) development system is the lack of connections between education and employment placement.
 - ❖ In Karnataka, vocational training is available in about 98 courses, the majority of which are of extended duration (i.e. of 1 to 2 years duration). In Maharashtra, there are roughly 120 short-term modular courses that teach skills that are more closely connected with job requirements.
 - ❖ Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) in Karnataka find it challenging to invest in skill development institutions in comparison to major organizations, resulting in the deployment of semi-skilled workers in many MSME firms.

SUGGESTION

Karnataka's strategy must be reoriented to meet the demands of people entering the working age group, provide skills training, and plan for challenges that will arise when this huge population retires. As a result, this section is devoted to depicting Karnataka's current skill capacity, as well as the primary problems in successfully implementing skill development efforts, and also their solutions or ideas.

CONCLUSION

A competent workforce is required to make Karnataka nationally competitive and to accelerate its economic progress. As Karnataka evolves more and more towards a knowledge economy, it becomes increasingly vital for the state to focus on skill advancement, and these skills must be relevant to the evolving economic environment. An effective skill development system is essential for converting the demographic dividend of the state. As a result, in order to meet its ambitious skilling goal, it is critical to have holistic answers to the difficulties rather than piecemeal initiatives.

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